

Chip-scale source of photonic entanglement

Jingyun Fan

Joint Quantum Institute, University of Maryland and National Institute of Standards and Technology

100 Bureau Drive, Gaithersburg, MD 20899-8441, USA

Photonic entanglement is essential to many areas of research, including quantum key distribution, quantum teleportation and linear quantum computing. Typical sources of photonic entanglement rely on 2nd or 3rd order optical nonlinear processes. These sources are inherently probabilistic, so to avoid unwanted multiphoton events they must be operated at very low mean photon number probabilities. Source-multiplexing offers a path around this problem allowing operation much close to the ideal of on-demand emission. We present our recent development of chip-scale devices for photonic entanglement.

Our original source design for polarization-entangled photon pairs was based upon spontaneous parametric down-conversion (PDC) in a periodically poled KTP waveguide. We showed that a specific choice of poling period allows two different PDC processes to be phase-matched at the same set of three wavelengths, with phase-matching condition given by,

$$\Delta k_{\pm 1}(\omega_s, \omega_i) = k_z(\omega_s) + k_y(\omega_i) - k_y(\omega_p) \pm \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda} \quad (1)$$

We showed that a single pass of the pump beam through a single crystal waveguide can generate entangled photon pairs with fidelity near unity without first creating two separate sources and aligning them with interferometric stability (Fig. 1) [1].

Fig. 1. Generation scheme for polarization-entangled photons. (a) A Rb waveguide in KTP, with crystal axes X , Y , and Z aligned along spatial z , x , and y , respectively. The Rb region is shown. (b) Two different ways to achieve type-II phase matching. (c) Two-photon interference experimental layout. The first dichroic mirror prevents PDC in the bulk KTP crystal (used to compensate for temporal walkoff). This bulk KTP crystal is orientated at 90° about the optic axis with respect to the KTP waveguide. The beams are then separated with a dichroic mirror into signal(s) and idler(i) beams and further filtered to remove photons from unwanted frequencies. The signal and idler beams are coupled into single-mode optical fibers. (d) The entanglement fidelity for bulk KTP, bulk RTP, and the Rb:KTP waveguide (WG).

Our second source design (Fig. 2) created a frequency-bin entangled comb of photon pairs from a silicon-on-insulator ring resonator side-coupled to a straight bus waveguide [2]. The coupling strength

between the two is determined by the separation of the ring and straight section. This separation also affects the cavity damping rate γ . Continuous-wave pump light at λ_p injected into the microring from the bus waveguide generates entangled photon pairs through spontaneous four-wave mixing. All three waves are whispering gallery modes of the microring. The output two-photon state is a frequency-bin entangled comb (Fig. 2(c)):

$$|\Psi\rangle = \eta L \sum_m \int d\Omega \frac{\sqrt{\gamma_s \gamma_i} e^{i[\frac{k''}{2}(m\Delta\omega - \Omega)^2 + \Gamma P]L}}{(\gamma_s/2 - i\Omega)(\gamma_i/2 + i\Omega)} \sin c\left\{\left[\frac{k''}{2}(m\Delta\omega - \Omega)^2 + \Gamma P\right]L\right\} a_s^\dagger(\omega_p - m\Delta\omega + \Omega) a_i^\dagger(\omega_p + m\Delta\omega + \Omega) |0\rangle \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2(d) shows the effect of bending on the zero-dispersion wavelength for both TE and TM fundamental modes of a microring resonator. Fig. 1(e) shows that there is an optimum pump ($\lambda_p = 1.555 \mu\text{m}$) for which the frequency mismatch, defined as $\Delta = (2\pi)^{-1}(2\omega_{0p} - \omega_{0s} - \omega_{0i})$ where ω_{0k} represents resonant frequencies of the microring, is minimized over a broad wavelength range (from $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ to $1.8 \mu\text{m}$). Deviation from the optimum pump strongly suppresses the FWM. For $R_1=8 \mu\text{m}$, there exists 21 TE and 19 TM comb pairs with 20-GHz FWHM separated by a free spectral range of 12 nm, for which $|\Delta| \leq 10 \text{ GHz}$ within the 500-nm range from 1300 nm to 1800 nm. On the other hand, a straight cavity (Fig. 1(f)) yields only a very narrow dispersion-compensated region regardless of the pump wavelength or polarization, demonstrating the advantage of ring-shaped resonators. Experimental works are underway to fabricate these chip-scale sources of photon pairs.

Fig. 2: (a) Schematic of photon pair production in a microring resonator side-coupled to a bus waveguide. (b) Cross section of both the microring and the bus waveguide. The crystallographic axes are designated for the bus waveguide only. (c) A frequency-bin entangled comb of photon pairs is generated when the pump frequency is tuned to mode number M_p . (d) Zero-dispersion wavelength vs. the inverse of the bending radius of an SOI waveguide for both TE (black) and TM (red) modes. (e) Frequency mismatch for TM modes for a microring resonator of $R_1 = 8 \mu\text{m}$ for three pump wavelengths. (f) Frequency mismatch in a straight cavity for TE modes with $\lambda_p = 1.407 \mu\text{m}$ (solid blue), $1.516 \mu\text{m}$ (solid red), and $1.649 \mu\text{m}$ (solid black), and TM modes with $\lambda_p = 1.405 \mu\text{m}$ (hollow blue), $1.514 \mu\text{m}$ (hollow red), and $1.646 \mu\text{m}$ (hollow black).

[1] Z. H. Levine, J. Fan, J. Chen, A. Migdall, Optics Express **19**, 6724 (2011).

[2] J. Chen, Z. H. Levine, J. Fan, and A. Migdall, Optics Express **19**, 1470 (2011).